

Effective Leadership with Z Generation

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Abstract

Leadership is visioning a place to go for the team and planning how to take the team to that place by inspiring, motivating and developing them. This process requires some prominent traits and values. Willingness, desire and perseverance are the first necessities that start the motion

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towards the appointed goal. In order for the leader to achieve a breakthrough at the end of the process, a difference must be created, contributed to the previous situation and a change must be made. There are many types of leadership styles such as; The Autocratic Leadership Style, Bureaucratic Leadership Style, The Leader Who Coaches, The Cross-Cultural Leadership Style, Emergent Leadership Style, The Laissez Faire Leadership Style, Strategic Leadership, Team Leadership, Facilitative Leadership, The Participative Leadership Style and The Servant Leadership Style.

Some situations may require different leadership models while for some cultures leadership may mean something different. However there are some common traits that the leaders must possess in order to have people to follow them. First of all he or she has to have the energy power to ignite the light so that people should want to go after. He has to have honesty, empathy, integrity and self-confidence. He has to be reliable, trustworthy and has to have good communication skills, charisma, creativity and flexibility. The new ways of leading must be taken into consideration and what may be needed differently done must be noted. In a world changing so fast, with all the new technologies, life styles, trends and generations, it's obvious that leadership must be renewed and innovated as well. Certainly some unusual traits will be valid in order to lead that generation, some of which are; awareness, energy, passion, different communication styles, more freedom, less leading with more revealing everyone's own self leading capacity, acknowledging the value of the power of thoughts and encouraging the belief that the world is so joined up and interconnected. This new type of leading must be examined in the light of the personal traits of the Z generation children.

Keywords: *Awareness, Interconnectedness, Z-Generation, Curiosity, Goal, Passion*

Introduction

Leadership is a philosophy of life in which our aim is to be whom we really are and to transform to whom we could be the best. Effective leadership is; understanding your team's talents and abilities as well as your own talents and abilities and working together with them by inspiring and motivating them to achieve your goal. Leading and managing are not the same things. In order to lead them a leader must get the group aligned voluntarily in full trust and motivation. The leader must have the frequency of energy that touches the souls' of his group. His values and traits should be acknowledged and admired by his group. They must have the willing intention of going after their leader whether he has a title or not. Leaders must have some special traits so that they can influence and motivate their group and encourage them, working together towards the jointed goal. These required traits differ from culture to culture and from situation to situation. Leadership gets affected by time as well because by the time technology changes, cultures change, life styles change and the most important of all is that people's expectancies and characteristic features change. Leading people can't be maintained the same way as long before when everything was so different. Leading Z-Generation especially must be considered in a different light because; they neither look like X nor Y-Generation.

1. What Is Leadership

"Effective leadership is providing the vision and motivation to a team so they work together toward the same goal, and then understanding the talents and temperaments of each individual and effectively motivating each person to contribute individually their best toward achieving the group goal." is a definition of leadership made by Stan Kimer a consultant on enterprise efficiency and

profitability issues. (<http://www.businessnewsdaily.com/3647-leadership-definition.html#sthash.r3osVuvE.dpuf>) Productive leadership shows optimism and provides positive energy for staff. Leaders are helpful by nature and truly concerned about others' well-being. Leaders find answers to challenges and are the first to reassure and inspire workers when things do not go according to plan. Leaders find ways for staff to work together and achieve maximum results in an efficient and effective manner.

<http://www.investopedia.com/terms/l/leadership.asp#ixzz4VSnPOzI0>.

The leadership begins with a vision and a deep-rooted commitment to the goal. It requires visualizing the steps and the consequences of the actions, inspiring and motivating the team. It also requires providing the team with using their full potential in order to contribute to achieve the goal. Leadership is getting people to move from a place to another desirable and aimed place by influencing them in a positive way. Leadership is different from management. It involves aligning people and setting direction besides planning, organizing and solving problems.

2. Types Of Leadership

The Autocratic Leadership Style: A lot of control is applied with this type of leadership. The leader expects his group to obey him and doesn't like to share neither the decision making part nor the responsibility.

Bureaucratic Leadership Style: The leader's behavior is characterized by a high degree of reliance on rules, regulations and procedures to which both he and his subordinates subscribe.

(<http://www.universalteacherpublications.com/mba/freeproject/p1/page6.htm#sthash.3AkndCEG.dpuf>)

The Leader Who Coaches: This type of training is encouraged by teaching and training. The team is

enhanced by the leader by knowledge and skills.

The Cross-Cultural Leadership Style: Not all individuals can adapt to the leadership styles expected in a different culture whether that culture is organizational or national. In fact, there is some evidence that American and Asian Leadership Styles are very different, primarily due to cultural factors. <https://www.legacee.com/types-of-leadership-styles/>

Emergent Leadership Style: A leader emerges and takes over the group but it's not so easy. First favors must be exchanged then the relationships must be maintained, developed and repaired.

The Laissez Faire Leadership Style: When people in the group prefer and enjoy working autonomously and there is trust mutually this type of leadership may be preferred.

Strategic Leadership: Strategic leadership provides techniques that focus organizations when they are deciding on their purpose and best business practices that are critical for remaining competitive and relevant. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Strategic_leadership)

Team Leadership: In this type of leadership anyone can perform leadership functions according to the situation, to provide effectiveness for the team.

Facilitative Leadership: Rather than being directive, one using the facilitative leadership style uses a number of indirect communication patterns to help the group reach consensus. (<https://www.legacee.com/types-of-leadership-styles/>)

The Participative Leadership Style: When people in the team are involved in the decision making, they feel less competitive and more collaborative.

The Servant Leadership Style: This type of leader shares power, considers the needs of the people in his team and tries to help them to develop.

The Transformational Leadership Style: Charismatic and visionary leaders equip their team members with new skills and transform them.

The Charismatic Style: The charismatic leadership style relies on the charm and persuasiveness of the leader. Charismatic leaders are driven by their convictions and commitment to their cause.

(<http://online.stu.edu/charismatic-leadership/>)

The difference between charismatic and the transformational leader is that; charismatic leader may only intend to maintain the status quo whereas transformational leader transforms his team members and the organization.

The Visionary Leadership Style: All leaders need vision in order to pioneer their team but visionary leaders know how to turn that vision into reality.

(affordanything.com)...good-to-great-by-jim-collins/)

Primal Leadership Style: In this type of leadership the leader has self-awareness and empathy; he leads his team with emotional maturity.

3. Leadership Traits

"When the effective leader is finished with his work, the people say, it happened naturally." said Lao Tzu. (pekguzelsozler.com)lao-tzu-sozleri) This summarizes how a leader has to be. In the first place a leader must have a vision. You're working towards a goal that's greater than yourself. It could be something small, like the success of the team, or a larger vision like world peace. Working towards a vision is far more inspiring than working towards personal gain.

(<https://siyli.org/what-is-leadership-what-makes-good-leader/>).

Then a leader must have the ability to motivate; if a leader orders his (her) team to do anything and get them do what he wants, this is managing not leading. If a leader is really leading, he causes them to want to help him. The leader has to have the desire to lead but not the desire of power. An efficient leader has to have knowledge of business, honesty, self-confidence and self-

awareness. If he knows his strengths and weaknesses then he knows his team members' capabilities and limitations and act accordingly. He has to have self-direction so that he can direct himself and the others powerfully.

A leader must have emotional intelligence and social awareness so that he can integrate people to cooperate, and so that he can move their hearts. He has to have ambition and tenacity together. Influential leaders have charisma, creativity and flexibility. He has to have good communication skills. Being charismatic involves communicating dynamically, with passion and enthusiasm whilst displaying positive body language. It involves thinking positively, having optimism and self-confidence. It requires being persuasive and building respect and trust of others.

<http://www.skillsyouneed.com/lead/risk-management.html>

Positive thinking and problem solving are also important traits that a leader has to possess. He also has to be considerate and empathetic. He has to be an effective speaker and a good listener at the same time. A leader also should remember that a genuine smile and maintain eye contact are prominent clues in order to keep the team on their side. An influential leader steps out of his comfort zone and displays the courage to take risks whenever necessary. True leadership sees where the company is headed and plans the steps needed to get there. Visualizing what is possible, following trends in the industry, and taking risks to grow the business are all required of leaders.

<http://www.investopedia.com/terms/l/leadership.asp#ixzz4VSnfIgau>

They love to learn and develop themselves in every way as much as they can. Especially they have the flexibility of adapting to the new technologies and new ways of doing things. They are open to all kinds of innovations. “The Roots Of Our Problems Are: Wealth Without Work, Pleasure Without Conscience, Knowledge Without Character, Commerce Without Morality, Science Without Humanity, Worship Without Sacrifice, Politics Without Principles.” Quoted Mohandas K.

Gandhi, which explains clearly how a leader should be. (indiacelebrating.com/essay/mahatma-gandhi-essay/)

We live in a constant changing world which is evolving and transforming incessantly. After Silent Generation (1927-1954), Baby-boom Generation (1955-1965), X-Generation (1965-1979) and Y –Generation (1980-1999), our World is welcoming Z-Generation who are quite interesting and completely intrinsic. Z-Generation has different traits and values which influence every aspect of life including the leading styles. First of all this generation is intertwined together with technology, internet, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and all the social media alike. They play with I-pads instead of toys, listen, read, text messages, send pictures and share comments all at the same time. They consume a lot and live fast. (<http://www.acikbilim.com/2013/09/dosyalar/nesiller-ayriliyor-x-y-ve-z-nesilleri.html>)

4. Z-Generation

Their IQ s and self-confidence are high. They are global and competitive. They make quick decisions. Because they have born in a very fast life their most specific trait is speed. They do everything so quickly, learn so quickly and consume so quickly, yet they don't have a high adapting capability. They expect that life will bring all they want to them and they are a little bit impatient. Besides technology is going on to develop at full speed. (<http://www.forumyokyok.com/genel-kultur-yararli-bilgiler/x-kusagi-nedir-y-kusagi-yas-araligi-kactir-ve-gelecek-z-kusaginda-midir-t25412.0.html>)

Generation Z, which encompasses those born roughly between 1996 and 2015 is coming of age in tumultuous times. They witnessed the Great Recession and what it did to their parents' jobs

and homes. They're living through a global pandemic that has led to record unemployment, an environmental crisis that threatens the globe, and political and civil unrest. This impacts how they approach work and life.

<https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/15873-managing-gen-z.htm>)

“One thing is loud and clear: Generation Z is extraordinarily socially aware to the issues of race, equality, climate and gender,” Wright said. “They are very much an activist generation. They expect leadership to be authentic about their beliefs. Like the millennials before them, Generation Z cares a lot about changing the world. They have a sense of purpose and want to align with businesses and employers that match their values and ideals. They are the ones using public transportation, eating less meat and avoiding fast fashion to help the environment. Gen Z is also driving positive change in their communities.

“They are not afraid to strengthen or cut ties with businesses that don't match their personal values,” said Christine Selph, “During the pandemic, 70% of Generation Z made an extra effort to buy from local businesses.” (<https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/15873-managing-gen-z.html>)

5. Leadership With Z-Generation

Other than the generation traits, the flow of life and the World order will change as well. If we try to draw a picture of that time; it is assumed that we will see more changes in the next 15 years than since the start of the digital revolution with personal computing in 1975. (Dixon, 2015, p: 41) People will have long lives maybe more than 100. So a period of many surprises, new skills, new jobs, new purposes and patterns of lives will be the question. (Dixon, 2015, p: 111) Despite all the developments emotion will be the force that will make the cube spin. (Dixon, 2015, p:12)

Under the light of this frame of Z generation traits, leadership styles will certainly change as

well. To begin with the authority issue, we can foresee that corporations will become less hierarchical and more collaborative with more responsibility and initiative distributed among the employees. (Drucker, 2011, p: 179)

The authoritarian leader who makes all the decisions will become a thing of the past. Instead of an entirely top down approach, the leader of the future will have to use a more collaborative approach. This will involve things like brainstorming sessions with employees and multidisciplinary teams to address problems and create a long-term vision. (<http://aboutleaders.com/the-future-of-leadership/>)

Liberating and developmental style produces achievement and improvement by enabling, empowering and giving responsibility while authoritarian repressive style with tight control produces limited depressed cultures. (Weeks, 2016)

This new generation will have different mind-sets. They will be aware of the psychological secrets of leadership. They will take into consideration the leadership models of Gandhi, Martin Luther King Jr. Lao Tzu, Sister Theresa and other spiritual influential leaders whom created a difference. An important criterion in order to perform an impactful leadership will be that; the leaders must not assume that they are superior to the people whom they lead. They must understand when to guide and when to step back.

Generation Z are self-motivated and entrepreneurial in spirit. They have been confronted with uncertainties, more even than the millennials, the generation that preceded them. As a result, they seek a job that is meaningful: salary isn't the bottom line. Furthermore, they have seen their parents' and older siblings' loyalty go unrewarded by employers, so for them loyalty has to be a two-way street.

They are digital natives who have grown up in the online world. They are progressive and

have had access to more resources than ever. They tend to be great networkers, which significantly improves their chances of succeeding at whatever they put their mind to. (<https://www.pageexecutive.com/advice/region/global/how-generation-z-redefining-role-hr-leader>) This Z-Generation respect leaders who are engaged and are willing them to give feedback. They need to be constantly heard, mentored and shown the bigger picture. They value face to face feedback more than telephone calls and e-mails. Generation Z proclaim that consistent communication is the most important behavior that a leader can practice. Leaders who check-in regularly on their teams, communicate with clarity and transparency, and intently listen to their followers, separate themselves from the pack. Being “up front” and “keeping up” with the interests of their team members is a priority for Generation Z followers. Individuals who effectively convey their message across channels using the appropriate encoding system, delivery method, and feedback loop (checking for understanding) increase their opportunity to be perceived as a leader among the younger generations. (<https://www.regent.edu/journal/emerging-leadership-journeys/gen-z-generation-z-leadership/>)

Gen Z has emerged as a pragmatic, risk-averse, non-entrepreneurial group that hasn't motivated by job security. Instead, a more nuanced picture emerged as they are explored. Their career aspirations, career development, working styles, core values, behavior and character, education, and stance on diversity are different from the previous generations. While salary is the most important factor in deciding on a job, Generation Z values salary less than every other generation: If given the choice of accepting a better-paying but boring job versus work that was more interesting but didn't pay as well, Gen Z was fairly evenly split over the choice.

To win the hearts of Generation Z, companies and employers will need to highlight their efforts to be good global citizens. And actions speak louder than words: Companies must demonstrate their

commitment to a broader set of societal challenges such as sustainability, climate change, and hunger. (<https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/pages/consumer-business/articles/understanding-generation-z-in-the-workplace.html>)

A longitudinal study is recommended to continue exploring the emerging leadership perceptions of Generation Z begins entering the workforce, and progress deeper into their professional careers and personal journeys. Continued research in this area will expand the growing framework of generational cohort theory and analysis pioneered by Mannheim (1928, 1952) and Strauss and Howe (1991, 1997). Delving deeper into the examination and understanding of predictive aspects and key characteristics of groups will provide further insight into socio-cultural factors and shared experiences that influence how a group of people close in age, having experienced similar formative events, interact with society. A juxtaposition of generational cohort theory and leadership constructs will provide a foundational baseline equipping those desiring to lead America's youngest cohorts.

From a practical perspective, this generation characterizes leadership effectiveness as those that lead by example, those that know their teams, and those that are team-oriented. Practically, these three competencies are invaluable to organizations today. The organizations invest in training, development, and evaluation programs that include these three constructs. Integrating them into the behavioral interviewing process helps to identify the next generation of high-potential talent and leadership for the organization.

Leading Generation Z is an open yet complex process. Leaders seeking to be effective across generational boundaries need to speak the leadership language welcomed by America's youngest generational cohorts. Leaders that practice a philosophy that places a high priority on

connection, results, service, and development best position themselves for stronger performance and organizational success. (<https://www.pageexecutive.com/advice/region/global/how-generation-z-redefining-role-hr-leader>)

Organizational leaders need to adjust their leadership style accordingly and place a high priority on relationships and team-centricity that promotes both collaboration and autonomy. It is recommended that intergenerational leaders communicate in a language that exemplifies purpose and significance, and provides an avenue for Generation Z to express themselves. (<https://www.regent.edu/journal/emerging-leadership-journeys/gen-z-generation-z-leadership/>)

A future leader should believe that all the failures manifest only when you begin thinking that you are failing. (Marukami, 2007, p: 97) Z-Generation leader certainly will have grasped the value and prominence of the power of thoughts. They will try to have consensus on common goal without coercion. Most of the principles of good leadership remain the same, regardless of how technology changes. However, technology presents new challenges for leaders.

(<http://www.leadership501.com/leadership-of-the-future/19/>)

Technoblind leaders have no chance at all. In the past, leaders were often able to rely on assistants for written communication. However, with the ubiquitous use of email, this is no longer an option. Leaders who cannot communicate well in writing will find themselves at a disadvantage.

(<http://www.leadership501.com/leadership-of-the-future/19/>)

Their freedom will mean a lot to Z-Generation, so they will prefer working personally without getting commands from their superiors. To acknowledge their liberty the leaders won't pursue hard on them. Leaders will know that to scold or punish them would only harm the relationship. (Lieberman, 2007)

Strong ego will precisely be an obstacle among the leader and the followers or employees.

Ethics will be the enhancing asset and the reliability will be in the first row. In order to get inspired by the most influential and creative persons, the value of books read and the persons chosen as friends will be appreciated and respected. (Sharma, 1998)

The profoundness of the relationships will go on enhancing the power of leadership in the future also. (Sharma, 2010) How to be a leader in that generation will mostly be based on the premise that they have, in fact everybody has the potential to be wise, compassionate and impactful leaders. (Bjergegaard, Popa, 2016)

As Generation Z pushes the boundaries of traditional work-models, HR departments will need to review their talent retention strategies. An extreme example is Buffer, a social media company founded in 2010 that publicly discloses its salaries. In 2015 surveyed employees regarding job satisfaction and pay. It discovered that the more information employees have about why they earn what they do, the less likely they are to leave. They seek transparency on everything and this even includes management. Additionally, flexible work models are something that many will not only be accustomed to but will also feel entitled to. At design software company, Autodesk based in the USA, employees can take advantage of a six-week sabbatical, and enjoy free meals and flexible working hours. Offering flexible schedules and remote working capabilities gives employees a sense of control, particularly around the work-life balance. It also boosts engagement and can help resolve talent shortages. (<https://www.pageexecutive.com/advice/region/global/how-generation-z-redefining-role-hr-leader>)

Such models aren't restricted to creative or start-up companies; large corporate enterprises are also taking note. They rightly recognise the need to review traditional, outdated policies in order to hire and retain this increasingly important element of their workforce.

CEOs need to be engaging and take every opportunity to communicate what they stand for. Marc Benioff, Chairman and CEO for Salesforce, is a good example of ‘going beyond business’. When his company was established, he initiated a 1-1-1 philanthropy model, donating 1% each of its products, equity and employees’ time to the community. Benioff is also vocal – and active – on social issues such as equal pay and human rights. His engaging and influential approach shows how an authentic leader can make a big difference.

As the prominent face of the company, CEOs and other leaders should show solidarity and a genuine intent to make a difference, or risk losing credibility. They must ‘walk the talk’, as ultimately employees will mirror managers and managers will mirror leaders.

Profitability is, of course, essential to running a sustainable business. But focusing solely on the numbers indicates a disconnect and a missed opportunity to identify and project what you stand for. The real challenge is retaining Generation Z, making it clear what the business is working towards and creating an attractive proposition for them. Leaders must consistently demonstrate why their employees have made the right decision in choosing to work for them.

6. Conclusion

To be a good leader requires some features which change according culture and time. We had a general view of how an efficient leader should be today and in the near future with Z–Generation. All of the listed traits indeed mean a lot. To gather up the subject; it’s obvious that in order to be an influential leader, he has to leave behind his title and his ego. Leadership will be more like a choice than a position. He will bring his soul to the driver seat instead of his ego. He has to have energy and passion together with powerful ambition and vision. This generation will absolutely realize that

movement is the antidote of despair because they already act fast, decide fast and live fast. He will be curious about different aspects of life and will be integrated in various activities inspiring his team as well.

If he wants to be a true leader he has to prioritize appraising the positive steps before correcting the mistakes. He will surely know that to be a human is the most important asset he has to display. He has to recognize that the body, the soul and the mind are a whole. He has to feed them all together and take care of himself. If he has a powerful connection with his core-self and the universe as well, he will be open to the messages that the universe will guide him. He will perceive the right steps and the right decisions. Primarily he will know for sure what his mission in this world is and why he is here. He will know the value of every living thing and be mindful. He will have the power of creation. He will support his team by cultivating positive energy. He will recognize the role of Nature in being a great catalyst for clarity, wisdom and creativity.

He has to create a space where others feel safe to tell their opinions. He will share his leading position. He certainly has to know to look from everyone's perspective and has to know how to resolve conflicts and misunderstandings. He will thank frequently and apologize when necessary. He will be in harmony within himself, with his environment and also in the universe.

Understanding our place in Cosmos is vitally important; otherwise whatever is done is incomplete and deficient. This leader must heed the interconnectedness. He must be truly concerned about well-being of others. He must believe in holistic understanding and mutual benefits. Everything must be for everyone's highest benevolence. The leadership with Z-Generation also will require humbleness, generosity and genuineness. Creating a better world is inscribed in our beings and it will be possible with this generation.

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